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Influence of Socio-Cultural Practice on Women's Educational Development in Abia North Senatorial Zone, Abia State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Girls and Women, all over the world, are subjected to a number of traditional practices that are not only harmful to them but also dehumanize and relegate them. This project attempts to examine the influence of Socio-cultural Practices on Women's Educational Development in Abia North Senatorial Zone, Abia State Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives from which two research questions and hypotheses were drawn. The study adopted a Descriptive Survey Design, which was considered appropriate in the study because it enables the collection of descriptive Data on various Socio-cultural practices that affect or influence women educational development. The area of study is Abia North Senatorial Zone. The population of the study comprises of residents of all the seventy-six (76) communities with 956, 594 thousand people with the sample population of 400 persons. The instrument for data collection is questionnaire. Method of Data analysis: the research question was answered using descriptive statistics of mean and criterion mean. This work examines the menace of wisdom-hood practices, early marriage, wife battery, female genital mutilation, inheritance and disinheritance practices on women and their offspring. When all that belongs to them have been taken or seized in accordance with the traditions and customs of the people. Women are not allowed to own land, not even by inheritance. Women are beaten by their husbands, inflicting physical injuries; there is also, wife abandonment, rape and incest, physical violence, psychological violence, denials of Economic right, political violence, obnoxious widowhood practices, women and girl child trafficking, acid bath, forced marriage and so on. This occurs more often at the death of their spouse. Again, female genital mutilation and early child marriage has also been a major problem facing women in their various community. Education is the only weapon that can spotlight her rights and subsequent assertion of same. Therefore, the need for every woman to be educated cannot be over emphasized. In conclusion, it is the view of the paper that elimination of these harmful customs and traditions will not empower Abia North Senatorial women but will lead to their development educationally, economically, politically, socially and otherwise. And the need to check them through instrumentality of the law.

Keywords: Socio-Cultural, Practice, Women, Educational, Development

INTRODUCTION

One Major concern that has preoccupied the discourse of contemporary society and indeed scholarship is the issue of gender role assignment. Every society has a perception of what is expected of its citizens which may be dependent on its gender. This perception is often constructed based on the social and cultural dispositions of the people. Depending on the cultural and social disposition,

there is an expectation for what should obtain ranging from dressing, choice of words, likes and dislike, public presentation and virtually everything.

These expectations are dominantly related to sex rather than to one's potential and capabilities. For example, the society has ascribed and subscribed to the notion that sports and any such boisterous activity is naturally a boy's affair hence, society has learned to associate engagement in sports as a measure for masculinity. Thus, if a woman engages in such "muscular" activity she would be termed a "Tomboy". Institutions such as the family, school, church and the mass media play key roles in the socialization process thereby, enforcing these gender associated role frames and expectations in the society.

A socio- cultural environment is a combination of social and cultural factors, due to the strong interaction that exists between them, society and culture have an influence on every aspect of human life. Socio - cultural is a term related to social and cultural factors, which means common traditions and belief present in a population group. The term is mostly used in sociological and marketing contexts and refers to the most remarkable drivers behind the way people makes decisions in a society. What is considered normal and regular in a society can be unusual or even extravagant and immoral in others. "Socio-cultural" refers to a wide array of societal and cultural influences that impact thought, feeling, behaviors and ultimately outcomes. Girls and women all the world, are subjected to a number of traditional practices that not only harmful to them but also dehumanize and relegate them. Related to "harmful traditional practices" is the concept of "Violence against women " the violence could be physical or otherwise, such violence could occur in the family or in the community (Weitzman & Gonzalez, 2020).

Nigeria as a country in West African, has been describe as "a land of contrasts and a melting point of ethnicities, religions and cultures (Offiong &Uduigwomen, 2021). The country has a rich and diverse cultural history spread across more than 250(two hundred fifty) ethnic groups within the nation (Offing &Uduigwomen, 2021). Each of these ethnic groups has its language and heritage. The largest of these ethnic groups are Hausa, Fulani, Yoruba and Igbo (Ekpo & Offiong, 2020). The traditional socio-political organizational of majority, if not all of these ethnic groups, is the patriarchal system of administration, where the men rule and run the affairs of the communities. The rules and control by men within the Nigeria communities have left the society with socio-cultural laws and practices that have put women in a disadvantage position. These Laws and practices have led to Social and cultural attitudes which have been discriminatory, and economic inequality within the various societies serve as barriers to their Social development (Offiong,2012; Offiong 2016). According to one of the Beijing declaration of 1999, and cited by Mojekwu-Chikezie (2012), "Sociocultural factors are major obstacles to women's advancement. Customs, culture, tradition, and religion have continued to relegate women in Africa in particular Nigeria to an inferior position of virtually no status thereby limiting their right to equality and freedom from discrimination within the traditional Nigeria Society, the Igbo women from the Igbo ethic group are the worst affected. Mojekwu- Chikezie (2012).

Within the traditional Igbo communities, women are not regarded when decisions are taken in community meetings in and most instances within families and homes. Their opinions are not sought even in matters that concern them crucially. The notion that women are expected to be submissive to men remains one of the foundation stone of Igbo's political, economic, and Social structures. That is why patriarchy has characterized several Igbo socio-political and traditional institutions; and this has influenced the society to a very large extent up to the present day (Mojekwu-Chikezie, 2011; Undiyaundeya, 2012).

The term Igbo is used as a double signifier. On the one hand, it refers to one of the three major ethnic group in Nigeria. On the other hand, it is used to designate the language of this group, the Igbo people of Nigeria. In terms of location, the Igbo occupy the bulk of the South eastern part of Nigeria. Igbo in Abia North senatorial district people are characterized by their culture which is orally transmissible from one generation to another through stories, proverbs, folktales, myths and wise saying that are primarily by face to face interactions.

An Igbo man in Abia North senatorial district is usually born and nurtured along traditional belief, values, norms and life styles. There is no gainsaying the fact that a person's behaviour is a product of his/her culture. In Nigeria an individual usually becomes a part of an ethic group upon birth, and is

immersed in the cultural practices prevailing in his environment. He is trained in the language, values, norms and traditions of that environment which form part of his development in life. Some of the cultural practices common to the Igbo people include; *Igofo* or *Igeoji* (ritual or libation), *Omugwo* (Maternity care after childbirth), *IbiUgwu* (circumcision) *ohunaosu* (Slaves and caste System), *ikwaala* (traditional propitiation), *iwaakwa* (initiation into adulthood), *inuiyi* (oath taking) *ibuuzo* (sanitation), *igbauche* or *igbaekpe* (traditional) retirement, and so on. Trial by ordeal and others in the form of sanctions include ostracism, banishment, widowhood ritual etc. Despite their positive roles in the behaviour systems, some of the Igbo cultural practices have been found obnoxious due to their harmful effects on mankind which, have called for a regular condemnation of these practices with a view to eradicating them without destroying the existence of culture in its entirety (Nwamaka & Linda, 2020).

The Igbo of South East Nigeria are predominantly patrilineal. However, there are some exceptions where descent is traced and inheritance follows the female line. These include Afikpo, Nkporo, Ohafia, Abam, Arochukwu and Egwu (2004) posits that through both the maternal and paternal lineages are important in these communities, the maternal relationships are the most significant culturally. Among the Igbo as in most patrilineal societies, patriarchy, that is the kinship system in which men dominate the power structure, both economic and political, and women are to a large extent excluded operate. This means that political and economic positions such as head of family; village or clan are dominated by men. Also, land which is the essential means of production in agrarian societies is owned by men. Women are not allowed to own land, not even by inheritance. In addition, the relevant decision making bodies such as the council of elders or the Eze/Igwe -in - council are dominated by men.

This patriarchal kinship system regenerates and sustains itself through socialization, especially through the use of language. For instance, among the Igbo, a popular adage has it that, "*Di nwanyibu chi ya*" meaning that a woman's husband is her god. The male partners in a marriage is thus elevate to the position of a god, making the relationship invariably unequal, A similar Igbo adage has it that "*Ugwunwanyibu di ya*", literally, this means that a woman without a husband has no honour. It is not uncommon to hear parents; even mothers exhort their male children to "walk or talk like a man," while the girl child is on the other hand admonished to "sit or eat like a woman". The Igbo society therefore employs language use in the construction of gender. (Stetsenko & Arieitch as cited by McKinley, 2015).

However, with the coming of foreign religions, especially the major religions of Islam and Christianity in Africa, the influence the and the role of women in religion were eroded, as a result of the ideologies of these new religions that favour the subjugation of women. For instance, the Christian doctrine advocates that women be silent and be less visible at home and in religious places. This is true as the Christian's holy book, the Bible, asserts that "the husband is the head of the wife" (*Eph 5:23 KJV*). As a result, the woman is silenced. Similarly, in 1 Timothy states that a woman should not "Usurp authority over the man, but be silent, and should learn to be silenced with all subjection" (2:11-12) another example in the bible is in (Genesis 3:16 king KJV), as a punitive measure to Eve, God stated that the woman's desire shall be to her husband and that the husband should rule over her. This interpretation of the Bible has been used as justification for gender roles and attendant gender inequality. Religion therefore, has aided female oppression and is hostile to the women as far as society is concerned. Religion in itself is not hostile but it is, only when it is perpetrated by patriarchal ideologies and interpretations.

In the social network of relationship within a given society, status is one of the most important social structures. Status refers to the level of prestige or social honor accorded to individual. It is therefore instructive to this study that as early as the 1920s when formal education, especially higher education was a status symbols, Igbo communities mobilized funds to send their sons to universities in Europe and American to the exclusion of their daughters. Thus, the status of men has remained above that of women among the Igbo in Abia North senatorial zone. Marriage among the Igbo in Abia North senatorial district is not consummated as a union of two equal partners. The woman is subject to the man. Thus the roles and positions of the wife and mother are subordinate to the roles and positions of

the husband and father. In the same vein, the male child is preferred to his female counter part for no practically justifiable reason.

It is against this background that this study is looking at the influence of socio-cultural practices on women's educational development and its implication for National/Educational development on the women of Abia North senatorial district.

Statement of the problem

A comparative history of women in Abia North senatorial district cultural practices has not been adequately studied. Focus has been on visible political institutions diplomatic events and intellectual currents of the high, as opposed to the popular culture and its socio-cultural practices against women in Abia North zone.

In the first (and most obvious) case, women have simply not been represented at all. In the second, they are seen as inferiors and subordinates to men. The third trend has been a conception of various obnoxious socio-cultural practices like Widowhood practices, female genital mutilation, inheritance and disinheritance, wife battering and early/ child marriage. Women are regarded as second class citizens in every aspect of life, educationally, economically and socio-culturally. As a result of this socio-cultural factors, there is no equity, no freedom and women in this zone are stripped of their rights. Widowhood rites in Abia North senatorial district portray situations where women are subjected to certain cultural that strips women of their rights. Sometimes they are treated like animals, subjected to do unprintable thing. These cultural and obnoxious practices at times lead to abuse of womanhood (Ebo, 2015). The implications of all these cultural practices is that, this Widowhood practices tends to make an already poor women poorer due to the long periods of restrictions from engaging on economic activities. The reality remains however, that the majority of Abia North women do not have access to control over resources like financial, and education that would make them less vulnerable to maltreatment and impoverishment should their husbands die. It is to this effect that this study is geared towards investigating these cultural practices and reversal through Government policies and instruments of law.

Therefore, the primary question which this study seeks to address is; Can Government, society (various institutions) and law help in the elimination of these obnoxious socio-cultural practices and gender stereotypes, in our society?

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine the influence of socio-cultural practices on women's educational development in Abia north senatorial district of Abia state. Specifically, the study was planned to:

1. Find out the influence of widowhood practice on women's educational development Abia North senatorial district of Abia state
2. Find out the influence of female genital mutilation on women educational development in Abia North senatorial district of Abia state

Research Questions

This study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the influence of widowhood practice on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district of Abia state?
2. What is the influence of female genital mutilation on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district of Abia state?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean response of educated and non- educated women regarding the influence of widowhood practices on women development in Abia North senatorial district.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean response of educated and non- educated women regarding the influence of female genital mutilation on women educational development in Abia North senatorial district.

Female genital mutilation (FGM) otherwise known as female genital cutting or female circumcision is defined as “all procedures that involve the partial or total removal of the external female genitalia, or any other injury to the female genital organs for non-medical reasons. Several reasons have been advanced for FGM, many of which border on tradition and culture such as ensuring better marriage prospects for the women, protection of their virginity, preventing promiscuity by reducing a woman’s sexual desire and increasing her faithfulness to her husband, etc. The physical health effects of FGM include pain and hemorrhage, wound, infection, difficulty and pain in passing urine and even death, limited to infertility, chronic pelvic pain, painful menstruation, cyst formation, vesico vaginal fistul (VVF), pain during sexual intercourse with the consequence of having a poor quality of sexual life among others. Psychological, FGM is often a very traumatic experience of victims. Traditional circumcisers typically use crude implements with questionable levels of sterility such as knives, razor blades, scissors and shards of broken glass.

Obnoxious widowhood practices

A widow is a woman whose husband has died and has not married again. Quite often, when women lose their husbands they are subjected to a number of obligations, demands and practices which put together are referred to as widowhood practices, some of them are harmful, painful and resentful as they are oppressive and dehumanizing. Practices vary from culture to culture and cover a wide range of rites. At the death of a woman’s husband in the Igbo tradition, where she is suspected to have contributed to his death (which is often the case), she is usually compelled to drink the water used in washing the late husband’s corpse in order to take an oath to prove her innocence.

A widow’s movement is restricted to her home until the husband is interred. She is forced to cut her hair and wear mourning clothes throughout the mourning period. Where she is suspected to have killed her husband, she is subjected to battering and banishment sometimes in a state of nudity and in some cases; she is inherited by the husband’s male relatives against her will. These practices lead to perpetual marital unhappiness and frustration, isolation, confinement, grief, boredom, anger, mental torture and hallucination. (Onyema, 2020). Some part of Igbo communities, widows go into confinement for a long period, sleep on bare floor, wear rags, eat from broken or unwashed plates and do not bathe for weeks. In Imo state particularly in Owerri and its environs reports a widow mourns her husband’s death for one year and during this period, she wears black or white dresses, she is not allowed to step out of the house for the first 40 days or cook or touch food meant for other members of the family. (Akpan, 2000). The widow is seen as unclean until she has completed the prescribed traditional rites. Many of these widowhood practices are harmful health-wise and inflict pains on the woman. It must be remembered too that during the period of confinement the widows cannot engage in their normal economic activities and this can lead to impoverishment. Consider a woman who hawks “akamu ‘akara’ bread, rice and other commodities every morning to make ends meet, and she is now confined; such a woman will now depend on the kindness of relatives, friends and other associates to feed herself and her children.

During the mourning period, some of widows are made to pay fines for violating some of the “dos” and “don’ts” besides, a woman may not be buried if she failed to carry out some of the widowhood practices or other cultural value expected of her. The combined influence of education, rise in feminist movement/campaigns and Christianity is forcing society to modify or even discard some of these widowhood practices. In the rural areas in particular, the practices are still very much practiced. Unfortunately, enough, the men do not go through such harsh traditional practices if they lose their wives.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a Descriptive Survey Design, which was considered appropriate in the study because it enables the collection of descriptive Data on various Socio-cultural practices that affect or influence women educational development. The area of study is Abia North Senatorial Zone. The population of the study comprises of residents of all the seventy-six (76) communities with 956, 594 thousand people with the sample population of 400 persons. The instrument for data collection is questionnaire. Method of Data analysis: the research question was answered using descriptive statistics of mean and criterion mean. This work examines the menace of wisdom-hood practices,

early marriage, wife battery, female genital mutilation, inheritance and disinheritance practices on women and their offspring. When all that belongs to them have been taken or seized in accordance with the traditions and customs of the people. Women are not allowed to own land, not even by inheritance. Women are beaten by their husbands, inflicting physical injuries; there is also, wife abandonment, rape and incest, physical violence, psychological violence, denials of Economic right, political violence, obnoxious widowhood practices, women and girl child trafficking, acid bath, forced marriage and so on. This occurs more often at the death of their spouse. Again, female genital mutilation and early child marriage has also been a major problem facing women in their various community. Education is the only weapon that can spotlight her rights and subsequent assertion of same. Therefore, the need for every woman to be educated cannot be over emphasized. In conclusion, it is the view of the paper that elimination of these harmful customs and traditions will not empower Abia North Senatorial women but will lead to their development educationally, economically, politically, socially and otherwise. And the need to check them through instrumentality of the law.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of widowhood practices on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district of Abia state?*

Table 4.1: Influence of Widowhood Practice on Women's educational Development

S/N	Influence of Widowhood Practice on Women's educational Development	Educated (N = 175)			Non-Educated (N=216)		
		M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK
1.	Widowhood practice strip women access to properties which in turn hinder their economic development.	3.69	0.46	A	3.95	0.22	A
2.	Widowhood practice limit women access to inheritance rights which prevents them from accumulating wealth/assets.	2.94	0.74	A	2.97	0.71	A
3.	Widowhood practice limit women access to education which is vital for knowledge building towards economic advancement.	2.30	0.46	D	3.01	0.86	A
4.	Widowhood practice can lead to social isolation making it difficult for women to access support network for personal development.	3.00	0.00	A	3.00	0.00	A
5.	Widowhood practice can lead to mental health issues which can hinder overall wellbeing of women.	3.86	0.35	A	3.56	0.50	A
6.	Widowhood practice may exclude women from decision making which could deny them voice of matters that affect them.	3.31	0.46	A	3.26	0.44	A
7.	Widowhood practice cause women to depend on male family members, thus limiting their financial independence and overall development.	4.00	0.00	A	3.84	0.37	A
8.	Widowhood practice reinforce traditional gender roles and thus limit women's freedom to pursue their aspirations.	3.70	0.46	A	3.57	0.50	A
	Grand Mean	3.35	0.37	A	3.39	0.45	A

Field Data

Result in Table 4.1 shows the influence of widowhood practice on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district of Abia state. As shown, mean responses greater than 2.50 for items 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 for both educated and non-educated women, indicate that widowhood practice has negative influence on women's educational development. For item 3, mean response of 2.30 for the educated shows that the educated women disagreed that widowhood practice limits women access

to education which is vital for knowledge building towards economic advancement. However, with mean response of 3.01 for same item for the non-educated indicates that the non-educated women agreed that widowhood practice limits women access to education which is vital for knowledge building towards economic advancement. Grand means of 3.35 for the educated and 3.39 for the non-educated indicate that the women generally agreed that widowhood practice has negative influence on Women's educational development in the study area.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of female genital mutilation on Women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district of Abia state?*

Table 4.2: Influence of Female Genital Mutilation on Women's educational Development

S/N	Influence of female genital mutilation on Women's educational Development	Educated (N = 175)			Non-Educated (N=216)		
		M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK
1.	Female genital mutilation could cause infections among women.	4.00	0.00	A	4.00	0.00	A
2.	Complications from female genital mutilation could cause long-term health issues among women.	4.00	0.00	A	3.84	0.37	A
3.	Female genital mutilation could cause trauma and thus impacting negatively on wellbeing among women.	3.06	0.74	A	3.23	0.49	A
4.	Survivors of female genital mutilation could experience post-traumatic stress disorder.	3.45	0.50	A	3.54	0.50	A
5.	Female genital mutilation could cause painful sexual intercourse.	2.37	0.85	D	2.87	0.77	A
6.	Female genital mutilation could lead to reduced sexual satisfaction.	2.69	0.46	A	2.95	0.22	A
7.	Female genital mutilation could lead to sexual dysfunction making it making it hard to engage in healthy sexual relationships.	2.34	1.00	D	3.37	0.73	A
8.	Female genital mutilation leads to complications during pregnancy and childbirth.	3.16	0.65	A	2.78	0.84	A
9.	Girls who undergo female genital mutilation could miss school due to complications.	3.69	0.46	A	3.95	0.22	A
	Grand Mean	3.20	0.52	A	3.39	0.46	A

Field Data

Result in Table 4.2 shows the influence of female genital mutilation on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district of Abia state. As shown, mean responses greater than 2.50 for items 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8 and 9 for both educated and non-educated women, indicate that female genital mutilation has negative influence on women's educational development. For item 5, mean response of 2.37 for the educated women shows that they disagreed that Female genital mutilation could cause painful sexual intercourse. However, with mean response of 2.87 for same item for the non-educated indicates that the non-educated women agreed that female genital mutilation could cause painful sexual intercourse. For items 7, mean response of 2.34 for the educated women shows that they disagreed that Female genital mutilation could lead to sexual dysfunction making it hard to engage in healthy sexual relationships. However, with mean response of 3.37 for same item for the non-educated women indicates that they agreed that female genital mutilation could lead to sexual dysfunction making it making it hard to engage in healthy sexual relationships. Grand means of 3.20 for the educated women and 3.39 for the non-educated women indicate that they generally agreed that widowhood practice has negative influence on women's educational development in the study area.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean response of educated and non-educated women regarding the influence of widowhood practice on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district.

Table 4.6: Z-Test for Influence of Widowhood Practice on Women's Educational Development

Groups	N	M	S.D.	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Educated	175	3.35	0.37	-0.96	1.96	Accepted
Non-Educated	216	3.39	0.45			

Field Data

The result in Table 4.6 shows the difference between the mean responses of educated and non-educated women regarding the influence of widowhood practices on women development in Abia North senatorial district. As shown, calculated value of z (z-cal) is 0.96, while the critical value of z (z-crit) is 1.96. Since z-cal is less than z-crit, the hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean response of educated women and non-educated women regarding the influence of widowhood practice on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean response of educated and non-educated women regarding the influence of female genital mutilation on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district.

Table 4.7: Z-Test for Influence of Female Genital Mutilation on Women's Educational Development

Groups	N	M	S.D.	Z-cal	Z-crit	Decision
Educated	175	3.20	0.52	-3.78	1.96	Rejected
Non-Educated	216	3.39	0.46			

Field Data

The result in Table 4.7 shows the difference between the mean responses of educated and non-educated women regarding the influence of female genital mutilation on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district. As shown, calculated value of z (z-cal) is 3.78, while the critical value of z (z-crit) is 1.96. Since z-cal is greater than z-crit, the hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between the mean response of educated women and non-educated women regarding the influence of female genital mutilation on women's educational development in Abia North senatorial district. This significant difference does not in any way mean that the opinion of educated women was at variance with the opinion of non-educated women. It only means that the level of agreement was wider between the two groups.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the following recommendations were made.

1. There should be sensitization of the masses on the dangers, pains and consequences of harmful widowhood practices. This can lead to a gradual decline of the practice.
2. There should be public enlightenment campaign against disinheritance, because the property of a man are the result of support from his wife (wives) i.e.; joint ownership.

REFERENCES

Abuah, F. A. (2015). *Change is coming! Nigerian women set to achieve 35 percent representation*. Retrieved January 11th, 2024 from <http://www.africaundisguised.com/newsportal/story/change-coming-nigerian-women-set-achieve-35-percent-representation>

Adaku, S. U., & Ndiukwu, J. (2015). The influence of disinheritance of widows rights and their children's' upbringing in Orsu local government of Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Current Research and Academic Review*, 3(6), 305-315.

Adam. Cotter & Laura Savage, (2019). Gender - based violence and unwanted sexual behaviour in Canada (2018) initial findings from the survey of safety in public and private spaces. December 5, 2019.

Anyanwuocha, R. A. I (2005) Fundamentals of economic for senior secondary school - Onitsha : African first publishers limited

Awan, Abdul Ghafoor (2022). Effects of early marriages on girl's education. *Global journal of management, social sciences humanities vol(4) oct- Dec,2020*, pp.856 _ 875- 894

- Essien, E. E. P., Gibson, M. K., Essien, C. K. P., & David, E. (2020). Effects of widowhood practices on the physiological well-being and socio-economic stability of women in Nigeria. *Journal of the Social Sciences*, 48(3), 567-578.
- Ihekwaaba, O. N., & Amasiatu, I. A. (2016). Influence of widowhood practices on the psycho-social and physical health of widows in selected states of South-Eastern, Nigeria. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 4(6), 49-61.
- Imagine, A. O. & Eraikhuemen, L. (2008) " An inquiry into sex differentiation in admission and academic performance at the university of Benin, Nigeria" in Benin journal of gender studies, 1(1)1-14.
- Kabir A. Raheem, Chikwendu Udenze, & Ismail A. Odetokun University female student's perception and prospective practice of female genital mutilation in Umudike, Southeast Nigeria. Vol 27, No 1(2023).
- Kalokoh, N. (2017). *The effects of female genital mutilation on women of Sierra Leone* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).
- Maria, Kiren, & Awan, (2019). Impact of socio-cultural factors on academic performance of students in district Multan - Pakistan. *Global journal of management social sciences and humanities*, vol 5 (2).
- Mojekwe - Chikezie, (2011) and Undiyaundeya (2012) African women sentence by tradition
- Mughal, S., & Awan, A. G. (2020). Effects of early marriages on girls, education. *Global Journal of Management, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 6(4), 876-893.
- Mukadi, E. B. (2017). Influence of Female Genital Mutilation on Girl Child's Education Participation in Primary Schools: A Case Study of the Tugen Community in Baringo County, Kenya. *International Journal of Contemporary Applied Researches*, 4(6), 188-198.
- Musa, C. N. (2008) "Gender violence in Nigeria: A review" in Benin Journal of Gender Studies, 1 (1), 85-96
- Nwamaka & Linda, (2020) " obnoxious Igbo cultural practices and panacea of the law in Nigeria.
- Niyi Adegoke Oyedolapo Durojaye (2021) Domestic violence and its impact on the educated women in Nigeria: vol. 19, No 3.
- Offiong & Uduigwomen ,(2022) patriarchy, culture and social development of women.
- Offiong. E Offiong (2012 & 2016) A panacea for skills acquisition for sustainable development.
- Ogundipe, A (2002). "Power in gender discourse" in Ukhum, C. E. (Ed) critical Gender discourse in Africa - Ibadan : hope publication. 31 - 44.
- Ogunwu, P. I. (1996). "Nigerian Women in Politics: Traditional and religious constraints" in Oruwari, Y. (Ed) Women Development and the Nigerian Environment. Ibadan: Vantage Publishers (int.) Ltd. 28-35
- Okecha, R. (2002). "Economic and educational empowerment of women in Ndokwaland" in Ukhum, C. E. (Ed) Critical Gender Discourse in Africa. Ibadan: Hope Publications 150-163
- Okoro, F.N, (2008). "Gender analysis of business education teacher/lecturers in institutions of higher learning in South South geo - political zone" in Benin journal of gender studies 1(1), 107-116.
- Rebecca , S. Bigler, & Lynn .S. Liben, (2006). A developmental intergroup theory of social stereotypes and prejudice volume 23, (2006). Pages 39-89.
- Silas, S. T., & Idachaba, E. A. (2020). Disinheritance and women development in Igboland, eastern Nigeria: A theological-ethical study. *Journal of African Studies and Sustainable Development*, 3(5), 15-26.
- Steven. J. Spencer (2016). Stereotype threat annual review of psychology vol. 67: 415-437
- Stetsenko & Arievidt as cited by McKinley, (2015) "the self in cultural - historical activity theory.
- UNESCO principal Regional office for Asia and the Pacific (1997) integrating girl child issues into population education Bangkok, Thailand; UNESCO PROAP.
- Weltzman & Gonzalez, (2020) Sociocultural, the concept of violence against women.
- Williams P. Akpochofo, (2009). Social Studies and Feminist Issues for Teachers Education. In Justice Jeco Press and Publishers Ltd.
- Yamane P. (1967). *Statistics and introduction* 8 (2nded.) New York: Harper and Row.